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TEACHER EFFICACY IN RELATION TO EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The present research paper aims at study the teacher efficacy in relation to emotional intelligence of teachers working at secondary level with respect to their gender and locale. 400 secondary teachers from district Sonapat (Haryana) were taken by using random and purposive sampling methods. Data was analysed with the help of Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation and t-test. It was found out that there is positive and significant relationship between teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender and locale. The results of present study have implications for planners and policy makers.

KEY WORD: Teacher Efficacy and Emotional Intelligence.

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INTRODUCTION

Teachers are very important in the actualization of the school goals and national development. In order to teach effectively, teachers must not only feel psychologically and emotionally comfortable, but they must also have some sense of belief that they can make a difference to the lives of children they are teaching. They must feel their professional work in bringing about positive change in their pupils (Edward, 1996).

TEACHER EFFICACY

A teacher's perception of his/her own efficacy is seen as affecting the effort

they invest in their teaching, as well as the goals they set and their level of aspiration in their professional field and career (Gordon & Debus, 2002). Teachers with a strong sense of efficacy have been found to manifest greater levels of planning and organization in their work, to be more open to new ideas and to be more willing to experiment with new teaching methods. They are more persistent in their teaching effort, less critical and more able to sustain empathy and support for their pupils. They have greater enthusiasm for and commitment to teaching and more tenacity in their work and profession (Ashton & Webb, 1986). A quality conscious teacher is one who is committed, enthusiastic, resourceful and intellectually as well as emotionally energetic in his/her work (Day, 2004).

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Emotional intelligence is a developing concept in the field of education. The early roots of EI germinated in Thorndike's concept of social intelligence. Thorndike (as cited in Wong & Law, 2002) identified social intelligence as "the ability to understand and manage men and women, boys and girls and to act wisely in human relations". Gardner (1983) abducted eight different types of intelligence out of which personal intelligence paved the way for the flourishing of EI. From among the theories proposed for EI, Reuven Bar-On, Daniel Goleman, and Salovey and Mayer's theories have been most influential in academic circles and have contributed most to our understanding and knowledge of EI. Salovey and Mayer (1990) represented EI as the ability of people to cope with their emotions. In their words, EI is defined as "the subset of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and action"

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

It is an established fact that the performance of a teacher mainly depends upon his psychological state of mind. As emotional intelligence affects the physical and psychological well being of the teachers, it definitely influences teaching effectiveness and performance of the teacher, (Gmelch, 1983). Teachers with high efficacy are more persistent in their teaching effort, less critical and more able to sustain empathy and support for their pupils. They have greater enthusiasm for and commitment to teaching and more tenacity in their work and profession (Ashton & Webb, 1986). It becomes imperative therefore, to study the relationship between teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence among secondary school teachers.

In the last decade or so psychologists have discovered about the role emotions play in one's life. According to Goleman (1998) from the perspective of work, feelings matter to the extent that they facilitate or interfere with the shared goal. Various researchers have found that success and happiness in life is determined by our emotional awareness and ability to handle feelings rather than our IQ. So a teacher with excellent academic record cannot necessarily be termed as a good teacher. Previous researches also show that IQ alone is no more a measure of personal and professional success. It accounts for only 20 % and the rest 80% is contributed by emotional and social intelligence (Goleman, 1995, 1998). Fiest & Barron (1996) concluded that emotional and social competencies were four times more important than IQ in determining professional success and prestige. Highly emotionally intelligent people are more punctual and take maximum initiative on the job; they put much amount of efforts to expand their job. This finding was also

supported by Cooper & Sawaf (1997); Tischler, et al (2000) and Thilam & Kirby (2002).

According to career ratings on the basis of the EQ requirement, teaching job stands fifth on the continuum from top. Jobs which require contact with other people or require one to empathize with or understand others, demand a high level of emotional intelligence. Teaching is one which demands high EQ level due to constant interaction with students (Yate, 1997). Numerous studies have shown that people with high level of emotional intelligence possess better profile of personal effectiveness (Sethi & Patel, 1985; Salovey & Slutyer, 1997; Goleman, 1998; Joseph-Hee-Woa Jae, 1998; Sharma, 2000; Singh, 2003; Pradhan, Bansal & Biswal, 2005; Bansi Bihari & Surwade, 2006; Sailaja& Devi,2010; Srinivasa, 2010; Sharma, 2011).

Today in this the era of science and technology there are lots of changes in educational pattern. Besides this, there are drastic changes in our social structure also. Now education has become child centered. So, the role of the teacher has also changed altogether. In order to play their role effectively a teacher has to be highly emotional intelligent. To what extent this EQ, Gender and locale of teachers can play an effective role; an attempt has been made in this study to see the relationship of classroom performance and EI of senior secondary school teachers of Haryana.

It is also essential and beneficial for planners and authorities to consider the relationship between psychological and teaching variables such as emotional intelligence and teacher efficacy of the teachers and should try to provide suitable environment in the educational institutions so that the educational achievement of the students at secondary level may be enhanced. Therefore the researchers made

an attempt to find out the relationship between teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence of teachers working at secondary level.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

TEACHER EFFICACY IN RELATION TO EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF TEACHERS WORKING AT SECONDARY LEVEL.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE TERMS USED

a) Teacher Efficacy

Here, teacher efficacy means the teacher's belief in his or her capability to organize and execute courses of action required to successfully accomplishing a specific teaching task in a particular context.

b) Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence means the ability to monitor teacher's own and others emotions to discriminate among them and to use the informations to guide students' thinking and actions. It is an individual's ability to perceive, express, understand and regulate emotional responses both internally and in others.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted with the following objectives:

1. To study the relationship between Teacher Efficacy and emotional intelligence of the teachers working at secondary level.
2. To assess the relationship between Teacher Efficacy and emotional intelligence of the teachers working at secondary level with respect to their gender and locale.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

Following hypotheses were testified:

1. There is no significant relationship between Teacher Efficacy and emotional intelligence of teachers working at secondary level.
2. There is no significant relationship between Teacher Efficacy and emotional intelligence of teachers working at secondary level with respect to gender and locale.

METHODOLOGY

For the present study, the investigators used descriptive method to study the teacher efficacy in relation to emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers. Keeping in view the purpose of the study the correlates and differential have been planned to be employed as analysis procedure.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE

Data was collected by using random and purposive sampling. Teachers working in govt. secondary schools in Haryana State were the population for the study. 400 teachers were taken as sample from district Sonapat of Haryana State.

Selection of Schools

For the selection of schools, the investigators first of all considered only district Sonipat of State Haryana. Out of different categories of school i.e. Govt. / Govt. Aided/ Private schools, only govt. secondary school recognized by Board of School Education Haryana, Bhiwani were taken for the purpose. Further, schools in rural area were selected by lottery method while all schools were selected, situated in urban area in district Sonipat. In this way, total 65 schools were selected for the purpose.

Selection of Respondents

Random sampling technique was used to select the teachers from rural area but from the urban area all the teachers teaching in govt. secondary schools were taken as sample. Out of total teachers 200 male and 200 female were selected from rural and urban area respectively.

TOOLS USED

For present study, the investigator used the following tools;

- i. Teacher Efficacy Scale developed and standardized by Dr. T. Pradeep Kumar in 2012.
- ii. Emotional Intelligence Scale developed and standardized by Anukul Hyde and Sanjyot Pethe in 2005.

SCORING PROCEDURE

After the collection of data from the teachers selected for sample, the next step was to score the responses on this measure. The responses of the teachers were scored according to the scoring procedure of the manuals given in Teacher Efficacy Scale and Emotional Intelligence Scale.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Mean, Correlation, and 't'-Test were used for analysis and interpretation of data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Correlation and differential between Teacher Efficacy and Emotional Intelligence has been studied in the following tables.

TABLE-1 COEFFECIENT OF CORRELATION BETWEEN TEACHER EFFICACY AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF TEACHERS TEACHING IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Sub Sample		Variable/s	N	'r'-value	Level of Significance
GENDER	Male	TE	200	0.22	0.01
		EI	200		
	Female	TE	200	0.18	0.01
		EI	200		
LOCALE	Rural- Male Teachers	TE	100	0.21	0.05
		EI	100		
	Urban- Male Teachers	TE	100	0.28	0.01
		EI	100		
	Rural- Female Teachers	TE	100	0.20	0.05
		EI	100		
	Urban- Female Teachers	TE	100	0.21	0.05
		EI	100		
OVERALL		TE	400	0.21	0.01
		EI	400		

TE=Teacher Efficacy, **EI**= Emotional intelligence

Table reveals positive and significant coefficient of correlation ($r=-0.22, df=198$) between teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence of male teachers teaching in secondary schools. Table also shows positive and significant coefficient of correlation ($r=-0.18, df=198$) between teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence of female teachers teaching in secondary schools.

It is evident from the table that there is positive and significant coefficient of correlation ($r=-0.21, df=98$) between teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence of male teachers teaching in rural area in secondary schools.

Table also shows positive and significant coefficient of correlation ($r=-0.28, df=98$) between teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence of male teachers teaching in urban area in secondary schools.

Table depicts positive and significant coefficient of correlation ($r=-0.20, df=98$) between teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence of female teachers teaching in rural area in secondary schools.

It is also evident from the table that

there is positive and significant coefficient of correlation ($r=-0.21, df=98$) between teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence of female teachers teaching in urban area in secondary schools.

Table reveals positive and significant coefficient of correlation ($r=-0.21, df=198$) between teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers.

So the hypothesis that "There is no significant relationship between Teacher Efficacy and Emotional Intelligence of teachers working at secondary level with respect to gender and locale" is rejected. The positive value of coefficient of correlation indicates that teachers who were highly efficacious with their job were high on emotional intelligence; on the other hand teachers who were less efficacious with their job had low emotional intelligence.

FINDINGS RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHER EFFICACY AND OCCUPATIONAL STRESS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH RESPECT TO THEIR GENDER AND LOCALE

- (i) Positive and significant relationship

- was found out between teacher efficacy and Emotional intelligence of male teachers teaching in the secondary schools. The positive value of coefficient of correlation indicates that male teachers who were highly efficacious with their job were high on emotional intelligence; on the other hand male teachers who were less efficacious with their job were low on emotional intelligence.
- (ii) Positive and significant relationship was found out between teacher efficacy and Emotional intelligence of female teachers teaching in the primary schools. The negative value of coefficient of correlation indicates that female teachers who were highly efficacious with their job were high on emotional intelligence; on the other hand female teachers who were less efficacious with their job were low on emotional intelligence.
 - (iii) Positive and significant relationship was found out between teacher efficacy and Emotional intelligence of male teachers teaching in the primary schools in rural area. The negative value of coefficient of correlation indicates that male teachers in rural area who were highly efficacious with their job were high on emotional intelligence; on the other hand teachers who were less efficacious with their job were low on emotional intelligence.
 - (iv) Positive and significant relationship was found out between teacher efficacy and Emotional intelligence of female teachers teaching in the primary schools in rural area. The negative value of coefficient of correlation indicates that female teachers in rural area who were highly efficacious with their job were high on emotional intelligence; on the other hand teachers who were less efficacious with their job were low on emotional intelligence.
 - (v) Positive and significant relationship was found out between teacher efficacy and Emotional intelligence of male teachers teaching in the primary schools in urban area. The negative value of coefficient of correlation indicates that male teachers in urban area who were highly efficacious with their job were high on emotional intelligence; on the other hand teachers who were less efficacious with their job were low on emotional intelligence.
 - (vi) Positive and significant relationship was found out between teacher efficacy and Emotional intelligence of female teachers teaching in the primary schools in urban area. The negative value of coefficient of correlation indicates that female teachers in urban area who were highly efficacious with their job were high on emotional intelligence; on the other hand teachers who were less efficacious with their job were low on emotional intelligence.

DISCUSSION

The present study reveals that there is significant difference in the performance of teachers with respect to emotional intelligence i.e. teachers with high level of emotional intelligence perform better than the teachers with low level of emotional intelligence. The reason for better performance may be because teachers with high emotional intelligence are superior in managing and understanding the emotions of self and others (Mayer & Salovey 1997; Salovey & Slutyer 1997). Self aware teachers have a high degree of self confidence and knowledge of their abilities. They express their emotions positively without actually threatening the students. High emotionally intelligent individuals perceive and manage their emotions in a better way and use them in their thoughts

appropriately. Solving emotional problems likely requires less cognitive efforts on part of these individuals. They tend to be more open and agreeable than others. The high emotionally intelligent person is attracted towards those professions which involve more social interaction such as teaching, counselling, administration and management etc. and they are more likely to have possession of sentimental attachment and interpersonal skills. Such individuals are more adapt at describing motivational goals, aims and mission as reported in the findings of Sethi & Patel (1985), Pradhan et al (2005) and Bansibihari & Surwade (2006).

Another reason for better performance of teachers with high emotional intelligence can be seen in their ability to avoid stress at work place. Application of emotional intelligence at the work place enables them to develop a better conducive work environment in three important ways. Firstly, it helps them to see grievances as 'Helpful Critiques.' Secondly, it helps in creating an atmosphere in which 'Diversity is Valued.' Thirdly, it enables to create 'Effective Networks' where differences are respected and individuals are motivated to work towards a common goal. (Goleman 1998; Bar On, Brown, Kircaldy & Thome 2000; Gardner 2006). Perhaps, these may be the ways which might be helping the highly emotionally intelligent teachers of Sec. School of Haryana to perform better in their classrooms and adds to group IQ, i.e. the ability of group members to harmonize and work together effectively.

Apart from all this, high emotionally intelligent teachers may exhibit responsible behaviour in front of the students. They are in a position to create a healthy classroom interaction. As a result, students are encouraged, motivated and take active part in all discussions initiated by the teacher. In other words, highly emotionally intelligent teachers try to give enough space

to the students' ideas and feelings during classroom interaction. Because of this, an environment of mutual understanding & trust and a group feeling is created where students are encouraged to communicate freely (Sethi & Patel, 1985 and Bansibihari & Surwade, 2006).

The results show that teachers with high level of Emotional Intelligence are better in their classroom performance than the teachers having low level of Emotional Intelligence. So, it is imperative that teachers are provided with early interventions that involve emotional intelligence skills building. Particular attention should be paid to improve emotional intelligence of teachers in early employment, which in turn help them to develop the same among their students. Inspirational subjects like art, literature, poetry and music help in developing an appreciation of the beautiful and sublime emotions in life. Hence, these subjects should be included in teacher education curriculum.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

Inherent quality of any educational research yields some recommendations for the improvement in educational process and practices. The findings of the present investigation are also examined in this light and the following implications are traced out:

Influence of emotional intelligence is indicator of the fact that there is a need to create influential climate that is potentially capable of enhancing teacher efficacy of teachers. This could be made possible by providing such opportunities in day today functioning of school. It gives not only energy and scope to the teachers but also helps in reflecting upon and demonstrates their psycho-social abilities. Further, 'Capacity Building' and 'Stress Management' programmes should be

organised with the help of subject experts. To improve the emotional health of teachers, short term courses on psychological issues are needed to be introduced during in-service. Suitable mechanism for receiving feedback from the stakeholders is needed so that on the basis of findings of the feedback, problems of the institutions as well as teachers can be redressed. It is also needed to provide conducive and healthy environment by the higher authorities in the institution for healthy relationship among teachers. Orientations, workshops, refresher courses and seminars should be conducted on current issues emerging in teacher education at a regular interval by the institutions, as these can help in enhancing teacher efficacy of teachers.

This study confirmed that EI has positive relationship with teacher efficacy at school level. Further to this a school administration could have been developed to ensure that EI factor must be incorporated particularly in one of the most crucial process of staffing and performance appraisal. Teachers with a high level of emotionally intelligent would certainly be an asset to the organization. An organization change strategy toward providing a much more decentralized working environment which provide opportunity in fair and fearless communication channels among teachers and the administrators which ensure that teachers would have freely able to communicate and express their emotion, use them and regulate to exhibit functional behavior which would result in greater efficacy and thus better teaching learning process and higher performance

REFERENCES

Adeyemo, D. A. & Ogunyemi, B. (2005). *Emotional intelligence and self-efficacy as predictors of occupational stress among academic staff in a Nigerian University*. Department of

Educational Foundations and Counseling. Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye, Nigeria.

Ashton, P. T. & Webb, R. (1986). *Making a difference: Teachers' sense of efficacy and student achievement*. New York: Longman.

Bansi Bihari, P. & Surwade, L. (2006). The effect of emotional maturity on teacher effectiveness. *Edu Tracks* Vol.6 No-1.

Bar On, R., Brown, J.M., Kircaldy, B.D. & Thome, E.P. (2000) Emotional Expression and Implications for occupational stress, an application of the Emotional Quotient Inventory. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 28, 1107-1118.

Day, Christopher. (2004). *A passion for teaching*. New Delhi: Foundation Books.

Easthope, C. & Easthope, G. (2000). Intensification, extension and complexity of teachers' workload. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 21(1), 43-58.

Edward Jennifer L. (1996). *Teacher efficacy and school and teacher characteristics*. ERIC Document Reproduction Service. No. ED 397055, 3-15.

Feist, G.J. & Barron, F. (1996) *Emotional Intelligence and Academic Intelligence in career and life success*. Paper presented at the Annual convention of the American Psychological Society, San Francisco, CA.

Gardner, L. (2006). *Emotional intelligence development programs for teachers*. Ph.D Program.

Cited in Research Papers of Swineburne center of Neuro-psychology, Adolescent Emotional Intelligence Research Unit, Swineburne University.

Gmelch, W.H. (1983). *Thriving on stress for success*. California; Carvis Press Inc.

Gordon, C. & Debus, R. (2002). Developing deep learning approaches and personal teaching efficacy within a pre-service teacher education context, *British Journal of Educational*

Psychology, 72, 483-511.

Mayer, J. D. & Salovey, P (1997). *What is Emotional Intelligence? Implications for educators.* In Salovey, P & Sluyter, D (Eds) *Emotional Development, Emotional Literacy and Emotional Intelligence*. New York: Basic Books.

Pradhan, R.K., Bansal, D. & Biswal, R.K. (2005). Emotional intelligence and personal effectiveness. *Hyderabad: Journal of Community Guidance of Research* 22(3), pp. 250-266.

Sailaja, S.A & Devi Uma, L. (2010) Perceived self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of adolescents. *The Asian Journal of Psychology and Education* Vol. 43 No. 56 year 2010, pp. 20-24.

Salovey, P. and Sluyter, D. (1997) *The emotional development and emotional intelligence: Educational implications*. New York, Basic Books.

Sethi, A. & Patel, D. (1985) Creativity, intelligence, emotional maturity and self acceptance in relation to teacher effectiveness. *Asian Journal of Psychology and Education*, vol-15 (4); 24-27.

Sharma, A. (2000) Emotional Intelligence; A theoretical perspective. Agra; *Indian Journal of Psychometry and Education* Vol.31, No-1, pp. 53-56.

Singh, D. (2003) *Emotional intelligence at work: A professional guide*. Response Books, New Delhi.

Sridhar, Y.N. & Badiei Hamid Reza (2006) Teacher efficacy and emotional intelligence of primary school teachers. *The Primary Teacher* (July & Oct-2006, Vol-XXXI, No.3-4).

Srinivasa, K.S (2010) Emotional Intelligence and work performance. *Indian Journal of Psychometry and Education*. 41(2) 186-188.

Thorsen, (1996). Stress in academe: What bothers Professors? *Higher Education*, 31(4) 471-489.

Tischler, L., Biberman, J. & Mckeage, R. (2000) Linking Emotional Intelligence, Spirituality and Workplace performance: Definitions, models and ideas of research. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*. 17, 203-218.

Troman, G. (2000). Teachers stress in the low-trust society. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 21(3), 331-353.

Vigoda, E. (2000). Internal politics in public administration systems: An empirical examination of its relationship with job congruence, organizational citizenship behavior, and in-role performance. *Public Personnel Management*, 29(2): 185-210.

Zingle, H. W., & Anderson, S. C. (1990). Irrational beliefs and teacher stress. *Canadian Journal of Education*, 15(4), 445-449.